

Short Food Supply Chains in Italy: Legal Definitions and Opportunities for Farmers

Problem encountered and objective

Before the regulation was introduced, Italian farmers operated without shared legal definitions of “zero-kilometre” and “short food supply chain” products. This lack of clarity created uncertainty regarding marketing practices and transparent communication on product origin, making it difficult for producers to differentiate their products and for consumers to identify reliable local options. The absence of a uniform framework also limited the development of direct sales channels and hindered stronger relationships between local producers and consumers. Law No. 61 of 17 May 2022 seeks to address these challenges by providing clear and operational definitions that support local markets, enhance transparency, and valorise freshness, seasonality and territorial origin. The objective is to reduce uncertainty for farmers, promote direct and transparent supply arrangements, and strengthen trust and competitiveness within local food systems.

Main results / outcomes

The regulation defines zero-kilometre products as those originating within 70 km of the point of sale, while short supply chain products may involve only one intermediary. This clarity enables producers to communicate product origin more transparently and strengthen territorial connections. The law also supports the creation of collaborative networks and local Food Hubs, facilitates participation in public procurement for schools and local institutions, reduces marketing complexity and improves access to support programmes, funding opportunities and local networking.

Practical recommendations

- (1) **Leverage the legal definitions** to highlight freshness, seasonality and local origin;
- (2) **Develop collaborative marketing structures** and local Food Hubs to improve distribution and visibility;
- (3) **Explore participation** in public procurement initiatives such as school catering and local institutions;
- (4) **Take advantage** of funding and networking opportunities to increase competitiveness and local market presence;
- (5) **Strengthen communication** with consumers to emphasise transparency and product origin, building trust in the supply chain.

Further information

Law 30/2022 - Provisions for the enhancement and promotion of small local agri-food productions

<https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/gu/2022/04/22/94/sg/pdf>

Law 61/2022 - Provisions for the enhancement and promotion of zero-kilometre agricultural and food products and those from short supply chains <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/gu/2022/06/11/135/sg/pdf>

Stakeholder perspectives on emerging models of short food supply chains: a mixed-methods investigation on the 'Km Zero Newsstand' case in Italy <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/s40100-025-00405-2>

About this abstract

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EU4Advice (<https://eu4advice.eu/>) aims to lay the ground for effective capacity building of Short Food Supply Chain (SFSC) actors, by supporting advisors as catalysers of the knowledge flow from research to practice within an EU network of SFSC advisors, and by promoting the integration of SFSC advisors into national AKIS.

